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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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DR. ANDREA MONICA R. BARBASA

Faculty

Northern Iloilo State University-Main Campus

abarbasa@nisu.edu.ph

“ADULT ME, BE HAPPIER”

All these marks on my skin- you called them battle scars;
They remind me of laughter and how happy we were.
Though time may promise to help me forget,
Still, the ache left- quiet, and yet.

When no one will accompany you- go alone;
Wander to places where anxieties overthrown.
Let safety wraps you in its quite heart;
Trespass the sign “private property and leave whole like ready to start.

Still, the scent of the sea and sugarcane,
Pulls at the memory: We once danced in the rain.
But now, with my books and my untamed dreams,
I owe myself joy—more than it seems.

Adult me, be kinder; adult me, I beg you-
Choose happiness, not just a fleeting visitor.
Knowing deep within my soul-
To deny myself joy today would be the greatest injustice of all.

